

Ethnomusicology And Multicultural Music Education: Zimbabwean Children's Musical Games For The Classroom

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: August 08,2023</p> <p>Accepted: November 07,2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Music Educators, Children's Musical, Games, Education</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10083940</p>	<p><i>Music educators and ethnomusicologists can contribute to the success of multicultural music instruction by maintaining a sustained collaboration effort. The provision of simplified music and musical activities ready for use in the classroom would assist music educators. This research provides new teaching materials boosting multicultural music instruction. Growing up playing these games, these selected six activities from many choices. Zimbabweans, though a randomly selected sample, validated these activities. Cle Elum/Roslyn Elementary School in Washington and Kutandara Zimbabwean Music Camp for Children in Boulder, Colorado, successfully tested these activities. Learners got the opportunity to compare games from their own culture with those from different parts of the world. This experience brought an insatiable hunger to understand a different culture through participation. Children learned the music entirely by ear, with linguistic challenges. The music educators I worked with appreciated the availability of such music. Children led each other in their own time, playing these activities. Instead of worrying about content authenticity, music educators teach with assurance as their concerns soften. Ethnomusicology and music education should regularly interact through such collaboration, with the former sharing content for the success of multicultural instruction in general music.</i></p>

Introduction

Ethnomusicology has made available a large amount of music from different cultures. Such research enriches multicultural music by providing games and activities. As a discipline of study, ethnomusicology remains a preserve of tertiary institutions. The drive to teach from a multicultural perspective has led to world music trickling down to the grassroots level, that is, working with elementary music educators. This article provides new musical games from Zimbabwe for Kindergarten to 5th grade. Further, this contribution is a direct effort to aid the general music educator in supporting their teaching of multicultural music.

Mark (1998: 177) notes much potential for collaboration between ethnomusicologists and elementary school instructors.

American music educators have turned to ethnomusicologists for knowledge and training in learning the music of other people of many cultures because the school music curriculum requires multicultural experiences for children.

Teachers are encouraged to design, develop, and instruct a multicultural Curriculum. This paper urges them to teach without feeling constrained by authenticity concerns. Teaching multicultural music is a social responsibility: Multicultural approaches challenge music educators to expose their students to cultures beyond their own. Generally, these results aim not only to assist the teacher but also to develop the learners' cultural awareness by participating in the music and games of the other.

Multicultural Music Education

Volk (1998) states that multicultural music education includes teaching local American, Canadian, and other world cultures in the curriculum, emphasizing ethnocultural characteristics. Bartolome (2010) cautioned that a sprinkling of multicultural music might happen in a curriculum. Still, as children encounter sound that opens other choices, such an approach fails to foster contextual awareness. Campbell (2008) encourages teaching that helps understand cultural contexts. Games, activities, and music introduce children to world performance culture. This understanding will lay a foundation for the introduction of other social contexts. With time, learners will understand why context is essential, but we as teachers must tread carefully at this level. As long as the music is in the classroom in another country, it is out of its cultural context. However, it retains its age relevance and assumes a new meaning to these unfamiliar learners. Campbell's drive encourages teaching from a cultural context, which is vital in laying a foundation that at the K-5 level, learners understand music and games

of their age. This music reaches the classroom; actual context becomes a reference as the school becomes the new playground, a new context.

While teachers may lament the lack of authentic materials and adequate training in world music teaching, as (Demorest, 2004) suggests, these two valued points should help a teacher. Instead, this should be motivated to achieve. Music educators have to persevere as practice makes things easier over a while. Anderson and Campbell (2009: 2) point out that,

A multicultural approach to learning necessitates organizing educational experiences for students that develop sensitivity, us and them" are reduced through multicultural instruction in music and other subjects. Learners develop an understanding of the world around them, fostering togetherness. As in any other subject, a multicultural music curriculum is a pleasant but welcome challenge fighting to make people of varied backgrounds understand each other. Multicultural approaches are an acknowledgement of the diverse cultures of the world and the US in particular. Investing appreciation in young children through music is one of the key elements through which a multicultural curriculum is beneficial.

Many teachers are keen on teaching multicultural ideas. The poser remains the source of content, choices, authenticity, methods, meaning, and other related elements. As curriculum designers and developers, music educators are in a position of empowerment that dictates and influences learning. Teachers are responsible for selecting concepts that make sense and reorganizing them to suit the children they teach. Introducing learners into the world rides on positive manipulation of their sensibilities using world music instruction.

Teaching and learning environment

In teaching and learning these games, everything should be child-centered. Teachers should find the best methods to teach children these games more straightforwardly and understandably.

In traditional African learning and Zimbabwe, in particular, children grasp music and games through oral skills by playing with other children and listening to adults sing or play. Teachers can adopt this approach and challenge their learners to listen and imitate in the classroom. Further, music educators can empower learners by allowing them to lead each other without the teachers' supervision, allowing children to learn by role-playing and participation. Music educators are also encouraged to apply an eclectic approach in teaching music as different methods cater to different skill sets in children. Considering that children learn differently, one method can only impact some children. Using Kodaly, Orff, Dalcroze, and Suzuki's approaches will enhance learning, especially in performance-based content such as children's games.

The songs and games are classroom content in the schools and camps where the writer worked. Children are challenged, through peer leaders, to practice without supervision. By peer leaders, the writer refers to those unassigned leaders' other children follow. Teachers could take advantage of such children because they help their fellow learners to grasp concepts faster than in the classroom. Teachers need to have confidence in them rather than discourage them because, in some cases, playful, rambunctious learners are good at such activities.

When we teach culturally specific concepts such as those discussed below, learners must understand musical texture, instrumentation, and all the related facets of music and dance. However, learners need to learn to own and live the new cultures rather than understand, appreciate, and develop aesthetics for them. All the games below do not have any form of instruments, so teachers are free to improvise.

Games allow teachers to select activities, develop pedagogy, and encourage leadership in their children as they negotiate their social groups. Cautiously use games as activities to introduce other lessons. Engaging and exciting activities are challenging to stop, and learners need help to switch to the next activity.

The contentious element of authenticity

The thought of authenticity in African music performance and teaching in North America makes many teachers uncomfortable. Muller (2009, p. 28) argues that,

Authenticity is a widespread and ambiguous notion in our collective imagination, despite its connotation of trueness and purity, it is a construct—a postulated standard of truth that we can, at best, approximate and, at worst, turn out to be a chimera.

The writer needs help to agree with Muller's assertion because there is an element of truth in the concept of authenticity. For example, a particular group of people exists. They have a way of life that includes particular music, dance, language, and dress. These are real and identifiable as belonging to a specific group of people. They are concrete evidence of a culture. The performing sense has no clear-cut definition as it is a complex concept. However, such belief is applicable in different spheres of life. In this sense, the author discusses children's games and songs. They are concrete and present and have withstood the test of time and modernity.

Handler (1986: 339) suggests that,

Authenticity encompasses diverse meanings ranging from genuineness and originality to accuracy and truthfulness (Trilling, 1972; Handler, 1986, 2001; Lindholm, 2008). In many respects, authenticity encodes the expectation of truthful representation. It is concerned with the identity of persons and groups, the authorship of products, producers, and cultural practices, and the categorical boundaries of society.

Unlike Muller, Handler's view of authenticity sounds tangible and respectful to different people and their cultures. It allows people to own and cling to something they do and believe to the point of being identified with it. Theodosopolous (2013) believes, "Authenticity is a cultural construct of the modern Western world." That is the Westerners and how they view the individual based on their behavior, speech, dress, and culture. Authenticity and individualism are close connections that cannot be separated. The above quote is an interesting view, which borders on aloofness but acknowledges that culture and people exist. Teachers are uncomfortable teaching music concepts from a different culture when they need help understanding the music's meaning, form, purpose, and context. The author salutes such fears, for it shows respect for the different cultures. However, teachers should grab the opportunities to experiment and deal with fears of authenticity.

Authenticity will always be an issue among music educators, researchers, and cultural owners. Its magnitude varies depending on who is talking: some are traditional purists, and others are open-minded advocates of hybridizing music. Media and performance demonstrate authenticity in such circumstances. At the same time, the music educator clarifies what they are teaching the basics of a given music tradition and then follows up with a more comprehensive viewing of the performance on video. Authenticity is relative, but whatever style or culture of music, the sound should be recognizable as belonging to a particular tradition.

Facing authenticity with a multi-layer of activities supports and fosters an understanding of this concept in both instructors and learners. The teacher is interested in the music and probably the games accompanying the music or dance. In rare cases, some fortunate communities may have an opportunity to watch a visiting group from the culture. Performances of culture best describe authenticity and other unclear concepts.

It makes sense to look at authenticity as a guarding principle to any form of music. Several social and musical values essential in African everyday life differ from those in the US and Canada. Meaning, context, performance styles, and gendered roles have transformed significantly. Strict contexts, purposes, and rites of passage, as in African social life, are not replicated in performances in the US and Canada.

In the African public and social domain, music is purposeful, contextual, and authentic, affecting mood and behavior. In Zimbabwean rain-making ceremonies, for example, some songs and dances are never performed in the public social domain because of their vulgarities and erotic, suggestive sexual dancing. In North America, such contexts do not exist or are insignificant. Such music performed out of context serves a different purpose. Traditional contexts become a reference. Such a scenario complicates the notion of authenticity. The American perspective has moved on to cultural interfacing, where teaching and occasional music performance has become the norm. African musical elements are unmistakable in whatever performance. It is recognizable by instruments, rhythms, and ethnic styles. Having these elements come out clearly in a teaching situation is vital.

In simulations of the world music context, it is fair to allow children to have a hands-on experience of different activities such as music, dance, food, countries' treasures, and others, Chen-Hafteck (2010) Campbell (2002). However, when it comes to teaching the actual music explicitly, it is essential to sift and teach children from 5th grade and under music primarily for their age level.

Performance and the classroom

Children's performances of songs and games allow them to role-play and simulate life fantasies laden with imitations of adults, animal movements, and characteristics. Cook (2013) notes that performance is a social phenomenon involving voluntary participation, either rehearsed or sometimes not. The children's games that prompted ideas in this article are performance-based, and teachers will make better progress by using performance approaches in teaching them.

Performing the music makes it more natural for the learners. They feel and live it, as Deighton (1992) suggests. Abril (2009) asserts that performance is all-encompassing: it includes professional performance, school children's performances, and other related activities such as demonstrations by teachers and resource persons. Performances help to demystify and uncover music and dance. Further, it allows participants to connect sound and movement, eventually leading to understanding meaning. Performance is a part of critical pedagogy, which allows the breaking of barriers between educators and learners.

Critical pedagogy, such as musical imagination, intelligence, creativity, and celebration, are engaged through performance (Abrahams, 2005). Ahlqvist (1999) advocates for active learning in the classroom. Children at the K-5 level need to learn their music in a fashion they relate to; that is the play way, getting involved practically.

With an eagerness and competitive urge to perform for their parents, children are motivated to perform. Teachers can take advantage of this to teach games and music from different parts of the world. Bailey (2001) argues that performing enhances the learner's understanding of the music's intricacies. Handling, meaning, and

respect are abilities that learners develop through performance. Performance serves to demonstrate that children enjoy learning music from different cultures. It helps children open up more to their peers and participate in music-making.

Why Games and Activities in the Classroom?

Teachers sometimes report challenges in motivating learners to explore and discover as soon as they commence formal learning (Rubin & Marrion, 2011). Teachers, in their efforts to include elements of music from other cultures, sometimes pick relatively progressive music for K-5. The result is that children find it challenging and get frustrated, and teachers may find it hard to motivate them. Elements that complicate foreign music include language, text interpretation, instrumentation, context, and approach.

Children find their creative potential, leadership abilities, and teamwork through musical games. Dramatic creativity, performance, and self-character growth develop. Children learn ways of life from other cultures by simulating other children's learning processes, such as games during recess. Engaging in children's games in the classroom allows the learners hands-on experience with the music. It demystifies the myth of the exotic and unfamiliarity and challenges learners' musical sensibilities, Schippers (2010).

Cle Elum – Roslyn Elementary School is in Washington State. They have had a Zimbabwean marimba program for over twenty years. This background inspired the author to run trials of these games there in collaboration with their music teacher, Miss Jacqueline Fallon. Kutandara Camp is a Colorado summer program for children drawn from the Boulder catchment area. Kutandara Marimba Center is a school that teaches after-school programs in Boulder. They attract children from various schools in the area and dedicate the camp to teaching Zimbabwean music. The author has consecutively worked at this summer camp for four years, from 2009 to 2012, introducing these games to participants. The writer opted to introduce the games at a children's camp because the children come from different schools. It made the author aware of those children who have been in contact with such world music. There is more time for games at camps than conventional school programming. The age groups of the participants vary from five to thirteen years. This development allowed some games to appeal to younger and older children. The author decided on the Kutandara camp because they only teach Zimbabwean music, games, and dance. It provided a suitable place to try these games.

Teachers sometimes have to allow children to be children in the learning process and let them learn how they play with their peers outside the classroom. This approach is practical in musical games. With the games below, children teach each other the singing, the game or activity, and its rules. Children play and revisit these games outside the classroom, significantly reinforcing class activities.

Musical Activities

The following are six examples of games the writer grew up playing with other children in the neighborhood and at school. We did purely social activities while not working in the fields or performing chores. We have had these games passed down for generations. Such games are slowly phasing out due to modernity, primarily the arrival of electronic entertainment. However, they are still found mainly in rural areas and high-density suburbs. We also modified the rules to suit our needs. Sometimes, we changed the rules depending on the number of participants involved. To allow control and visibility, participants perform in a circle.

Game 1: Jongwe Guru (Chief Rooster)

Language: The songs are all in Shona, one of the three main languages of Zimbabwe, the others being English and Ndebele. The text includes vocable "nonsense" words that fill in melodies and rhythms in some songs.

Rules: Participants stand in a circle, and one child calls the song as others respond. Leading is a critical part of how these activities develop. Everybody is facing inside the circle, clapping the downbeats and singing. Inside a circle are two challengers. Hands are either folded or to the side. In the circle, two participants hopped up and down on one leg. The hope is the downbeat going on with the clap, interrupted by bumping. A new challenger comes in after one stumble. However, this is all very friendly and lighthearted. Players should not raise their elbows lest they hurt each other. It is fair to give all participants a chance inside the circle. Getting in the circle allows everybody to take centre stage rather than only clap in the background. Teachers can be creative with the inside circle events, clapping hands, stomping, or another movement instead of bumping each other.

Music

Jongwe Guru
Traditional Children's Game

$\text{♩} = 110$

Call

Response

Hand Claps

C

R

HC

Jongwe guru - big rooster
(*jaun gwaē gue rue*)

ndiani -
(*ndee ah nee*)

ndimambo -
(*ndee malm boe*)

The musical score is written in 4/4 time with a tempo of 110 beats per minute. It consists of six parts: Call, Response, Hand Claps, C, R, and HC. The Call part has lyrics 'Jo - ngwe gu - ru' and 'Jo -'. The Response part has lyrics 'ndi - a - ni?'. The Hand Claps part is a rhythmic accompaniment. The C part has lyrics '- ngwe gu - ru' and 'Jo - ngwe gu - ru'. The R part has lyrics 'ndi - ma - mbo!' and 'ndi - ma - mbo!'. The HC part is a rhythmic accompaniment. The score includes various musical notations such as triplets, first and second endings, and repeat signs.

Figure 1: Transcribed by The Author

Game 2: TsuruDarika Mutanda (Rabbit jump the log)

Rules: While we used actual logs in the villages, such games used other city objects. The class can stand on one side or in a circle as they sing for the log jumpers. Depending on the object's length in the middle, they could be two to four jumpers at one given time. This game is physical and tiring for jumpers, so they rotate frequently. The teacher can make the jumps a choreography, either jumping on the beat, in opposition or in any other sensible manner. There are no strict conventions.

TsuruDarika Mutanda

Tsuru

Traditional Children's Game

$\text{♩} = 120$

Call

Tsu-ro Se-ri-yo Tsuru wo-ya

Response

Da-ri-ka mi-ta-nda Da-ri-ka mi-ta-nda Da-ri-ka mi-ta-nda

Hand Clap

C

Se-ri-yo Tsu - ro Se-ri-yo

R

Da-ri-ka mi-ta-nda Da-ri-ka mi-ta-nda Da-ri-ka mi-ta-nda

HC

Tsuru - rabbit
(tsu ro)

Darika mutanda - jump over the leg
(da-ri-ka mi-ta-nda)

Seriyo - go behind [the leg]
(se-ri-yo)

Figure 2: Transcribed by The Author

Game 3: Kana Ndikadai (If I Do This)

Rules: In a circle, one child leads the singing. One person goes in the middle or within the circle and comes up with action. The rest of the group has to respond to the action by imitating it back to the person who started it. Giving all children a chance to come up with the action is highly encouraged as it helps build self-confidence.

Kana Ndikadai

Kana Ndikadai

Traditional Children's Game

$\text{♩} = 110$

Call

Response

Hand Claps

Ka - na ndi-ka-dai ka-na ndi-ka-dai zva - sha - mi-sa! zva-sha - mi-sa! Ka
zva-sha - mi-sa!

Kana ndikadai -
(kah nah-ee dah dah ee)
zvashamisa -
(zhah zlah-ee zah)

Figure 3: Transcribed by The Author

Game 4: MhoteMhote (Vocables words)

Rules: This game can be fun when the learners know each other well. The class sits down in a circle, singing call and response. One person starts going around outside the circle as everybody sits facing inside. The initial player picks their choice partner in singing style. The leading is passed from person to person soon after making a choice.

MhoteMhote

Mhote Mhote

Traditional Children's Game

$\text{♩} = 60$

Call

Mho - te mho - te Ndi-no-tsva-ga wa - ngu

Response

za - ka - ri - ye - nde za - ka - ri - ye - nde

Hand Claps

C

mu - su - ki - we ndi - ro Si-mu - ka ha - nde

R

za - ka - ri - ye - nde za - ka - ri - ye - nde

HC

mhote mhote - listen, listen
(moo mee mee mee)

zakariyende
(zoh kah mee mee dee)

ndinotsvaga wangu - I am looking for (someone?)
(ndee mee shah gah roohi gah)

musuki wendiro - someone who can ...
(moo mee mee mee dee mee)

simituka hande -
(mee mee kah kah dee)

Figure 4: Transcribed by The Author

Game 5: Tomato So!

Language: "So" in this game means 'like this,' a placement word with one English word, tomato. The song was composed based on a tomato source. It is an urban game.

Rules: This game is similar to game 3, where participants imitate the dance movements of the person leading. Children are again in a circle or any other formation that works. They sing the song with one child leading the singing as others respond. The lead singer does an action or dance, the rest of the class has to imitate the movement, and the leader passes the initiative to the next pupil. The game continues like this until everybody gets an opportunity to go.

Tomato So!

Tomato So

Contemporary Childrens' Game

♩ = 120

Unison

Te-ma-to so so so so so so, To-ma-to

Hand Claps

U

so so so so. E-li-so ge ge sh ge ge ge ge. E-li-so

Spoken chant

HC

U

ge ge ge ge

HC

Tomato so -
(te mah te ase)

Eliasa ge
(a'e te ash geh)

Figure 5: Transcribe by The Author

Game 6: PasiPameraZiso (Earth has grown an eye)

Rules: For this game, children stand in a circle. We played this game in the village and drew an eye on the bare ground. In the classroom, use a prop substitute. Children move slowly in a circle as they sing, responding to a lead singer. As they respond, they point to the eye on the ground every time they sing the word ziso. Others act in front of the eye as it is perceived to see.

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